

THE EFFECTS OF DEMONETIZATION ON THE FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF INDIAN NSE-CNX BANKS USING CAMEL MODEL

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ABSTRACT

The CAMEL rating system is a recognized international rating system that bank supervisory authorities use in order to rate financial institutions according to six factors represented by the acronym "CAMEL" Supervisory authorities assign each bank a score on a scale. Researcher has sampled 8 NSE-CNX Indian Nationalized Banks in which four Banks from Public Sector and other four Banks from Private Sector. This research study endeavor to find out the effects of demonetization on the NSE-CNX Banks financial performance through using the CAMEL Model. Demonetization is the act of stripping a currency unit of its status as legal tender. In The banks' data, before and after demonetization, have been analyzed and tested with Excel Hypothesis Testing tool on the basis of five different parameters of CAMEL Model to find out the significant effects of Demonetization policy.

Keywords: NSE-CNX Banks, Demonetization, *CAMEL Model*

I. INTRODUCTION

The government of India took a bold step to demonetize Rs 500 and Rs 1000 currency, which means that the legal tender of currency units is declared invalid from the specified date. This Demonetization of 500 and 1000 notes was implemented on 8th November, 2016. Demonetization of currency means discontinuity of the said currency from circulation and replacing it with a new currency. The surgical blow on black money called "demonization" has brought tremendous changes in all sectors of the country. Banks are not exceptional from the effect of demonization and have made sensations in operations as well as the products and services of banks. This has led to an increase in demand for digital banking, with priority given to non-cash transactions. The daily operations of banks are affected and there is difficulty managing liquidity and employees. This has resulted in a greater impact on liquidity

management and customer demand for exchange of cash, while reducing risk and maximizing the quality of service. At the same time meeting the directions of the Reserve Bank of India was an encounter. Thus it has been very significant to identify the effects of Demonetization policy on the Indian NSE-CNX Banks' financial performance.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Suita Singal (2017) conducted research on identity removal and e-banking in India. A case study was conducted to ascertain the level of awareness among rural India's population of e-banking facilities and the amount of increase after removal of identity. A sample of 100 samples was used with the ANOVA test to show that the rural population is very different with the urban population in the level of awareness as well as the level of use of electronic banking services. It has been shown that young urban males have greater awareness and use of electronic banking. The study would also help banks improve their e-banking facilities.

(Pseudo-January, 2017) According to the author's demonization, it can be said to be a surgical blow on black money, terrorism, fake currency, unregulated trading, real estate, stock market etc. within 3 days of that Arbor's blatant decision. 35,000 crores were deposited in the banks and rounded Rs. 1,500 crores of black money were destroyed. The author pointed out the various reasons behind distortions such as counterfeit currency, black money, more stability in the future economy, restricting the use of black money by political parties, unregulated trading and a less monetary economy. The author studied the effect of deformation on the three sectors that contribute to GDP, namely agriculture, manufacturing and services. With the help of a few data, the author concluded that displacement has adversely affected all three sectors in the short term only, but in the long run may bring many favorable aspects to these sectors.

Manpert Core (2017) conducted a study on the removal of identity and its impact on the non-monetary payment system. He said that the non-monetary system in the economy has many less fruitful, time-consuming, less expensive, less paper transactions etc., he expected that the future transaction system in all sectors is a non-cash transaction system.

Vijay and Shiva (2016) examined the removal of Satan and his full financial integration. They considered that emancipation awards were highly encouraging, and that the removal of identity was the long-term interest of the country. They gave them temporary pain but studied financial lessons. This has affected banking industries to make a significant investment in digitizing banking services.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Objectives

- ❖ To analyze and Compare financial performance of NSE-CNX Banks employing CAMEL Model between 2015-16 and 2016-17 Year Financial Data.
- ❖ To find out the effects of Demonetization on financial performance of NSE-CNX Banks employing CAMEL Model

Statement of Problem

The recent Demonetization has affected many sectors of which Banking Sector is one of them. Thus, the researcher wants to analyze the financial performance of the NSE-CNX Banks by using the CAMEL model between the Year 2015-16 and 2016-17 to scrutinize the effect of Demonetization in the financial performance.

Scope and Limitations Of Study

The scope of this study is limited up to NSE-CNX Indian Nationalized banks only, while the time period of the study was limited to only Two years Banks Financial data.

Collection of Data & Tools Used

For this study, Researcher has used Secondary source of Data Such as Banks Websites, Banks Journals, and Annual Reports of Bank etc. Data tabulation, analysis tools and Hypothesis tests are used to apply CAMEL Model in each Bank.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS & HYPOTHESIS TESTING

1) C – Capital Adequacy

Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) or Capital to Risk Assets Ratio (CRAR)

As per the latest RBI norms, banks in India should have a CAR of 9%. It is arrived at by dividing the Tier I and Tier II capital by risk weighted assets. Tier I capital includes equity capital and free reserves. Tier II capital comprises sub-ordinate debt of 5-7 year tenure. The main reason for the rise in Risk Weighted Assets and decline in CAR is constant increase in advances over the last few years.

Hypothesis Testing

H₀: There is no significant effect of Demonetization on the CAR of NSE-CNX Banks (D=0)

H₀: There is significant effect of Demonetization on the CAR of NSE-CNX Banks (D≠0)

Years	SBI	CORP	PNB	BOB	ICICI	AXIS	HDFC	YES
2015-16	13.12	10.56	11.28	13.17	16.64	15.29	15.53	16.5
2016-17	13.11	11.32	11.66	13.17	17.39	14.95	14.6	17.07
Deviation (d)	0.01	-0.76	-0.38	0	-0.75	0.34	0.93	-0.57

The above data, HDFC Bank have maximum Absolute deviation whereas BOB does not have any deviation. Thus we can inference that the HDFC Bank has significant effect of Demonetization. These Two years Data are tested using excel Hypothesis Testing tool and the following is the output of excel:

The above data are tested using t-Test for Paired Two Sample Means. This is two tail test ((D≠0) assuming $\alpha=0.05$, in above table observed t value is -0.71 which falls between the t critical value ± 2.36 . Thus we may conclude that there is no significant effect of Demonetization on the CAR of NSE-CNX Banks.

2) A – ASSET QUALITY

Gross NPAs to Total Assets:

Gross NPAs are gross provisions on NPAs and Total Assets considered are net of revaluation reserves. The quality of loan is one of the crucial aspects of that decide the health of banks. This ratio indicates the percentage of gross NPAs to total assets. Ratio does not give any tolerable or

t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means		
	Variable 1	Variable 2
Mean	14.01125	14.15875
Variance	5.416983929	5.159555357
Observations	8	8
Pearson Correlation	0.967654472	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	7	
t Stat	-0.710136872	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.250292795	
t Critical one-tail	1.894578605	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.50058559	
t Critical two-tail	2.364624252	

desirable limit. But it should be below 10 %.

HYPOTHESIS TESTING

H0: There is no significant effect of Demonetization on the Gross NPAs to Total Assets ratio of NSE-CNX Banks (D=0)

H0: There no significant effect of Demonetization on the Gross NPAs to Total Assets ratio of NSE-CNX Banks

(D≠0)

Chavda & Trivedi (2018) “The effects of Demonetization on the Financial Performance of Indian NSE-CNX Banks Using CAMEL Model”

Years	SBI	CORP	PNB	BOB	ICICI	AXIS	HDFC	YES
2015-16	4.35	6.19	8.36	6.04	5.9	4.05	0.83	0.01
2016-17	4.15	6.88	7.69	6.15	5.46	3.54	0.68	0.94
Deviation (d)	0.2	-0.69	0.67	-0.11	0.44	0.51	0.15	-0.93

The above data, YES Bank have maximum Absolute deviation whereas BOB have minimum Absolute deviation. Thus we can inference that the YES Bank has significant effect of Demonetization and BOB Bank has least effect of Demonetization. The above two years Data are tested using excel Hypothesis Testing tool and the following is the output of excel:

This data are tested using t-Test for Paired Two Sample Means. This is two tail test ($D \neq 0$) assuming $\alpha=0.05$, in above table observed t value is 0.15 which is between the t critical value ± 2.36 . Thus we may conclude that the There is no significant effect of Demonetization on the Gross NPAs to Total Assets ratio of NSE-CNX Banks.

t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means		
	Variable 1	Variable 2
Mean	4.46625	4.43625
Variance	7.9903125	6.823169643
Observations	8	8
Pearson Correlation	0.980762251	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	7	
t Stat	0.147677828	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.443380377	
t Critical one-tail	1.894578605	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.886760754	
t Critical two-tail	2.364624252	

3) M – MANAGEMENT

Management is the most important ingredient that ensures sound functioning of banks. With increased competition in the Indian banking sector, efficiency and effectiveness have become the rule as banks constantly strive to improve the productivity of their employees. The major improvements in the style of management and productivity have come about in the all sectors of banks. Today, it is not

uncommon to see the extended working hours, flexible time schedules, outsourcing marketing, etc. to attract and retain customers. The parameters used to assess the quality of management gives the measurement of the efficiency and effectiveness of management. The ratios of this segment are:

Return on Net Worth (RONW): Net Profit / Net Worth X 100

It is a measure of the profitability of a company. PAT is expressed as a percentage of Average Net Worth. This ratio expresses the net profit in terms of net worth. This ratio is an important yardstick of performance for equity shareholders since it indicates the return on the funds employed by them. Though, YES Bank has highest Ratio in terms of Return on Net worth.

HYPOTHESIS TESTING

H0: There is no significant effect of Demonetization on the RONW ratio of NSE-CNX Banks (D=0)

H0: There no significant effect of Demonetization on the RONW ratio of NSE-CNX Banks (D≠0)

Years	SBI	CORP	PNB	BOB	ICICI	AXIS	HDFC	YES
2015-16	6.89	-4.73	-11.2	-13.42	11.19	15.46	16.91	18.41
2016-17	6.69	4.65	3.47	3.43	10.11	6.59	16.26	15.09
Deviation (d)	0.2	-9.38	-14.67	-16.85	1.08	8.87	0.65	3.32

So far as RONW Ratio is concerned, BOB Bank has maximum Absolute deviation whereas SBI have minimum Absolute deviation. Thus we can say that the BOB Bank has maximum effect of Demonetization and SBI Bank has least effect of Demonetization. These two years Data are tested using excel Hypothesis Testing tool and the following is the out of excel:

The above data are tested using t-Test for Paired Two Sample Means. This is two tail test ((D≠0) assuming $\alpha=0.05$, in the above table observed t value is -1.03 which lies between the t critical

t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means		
	Variable 1	Variable 2
Mean	4.93875	8.28625
Variance	167.0507554	25.51782679
Observations	8	8
Pearson Correlation	0.830561649	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	7	
t Stat	-1.032360679	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.168123165	
t Critical one-tail	1.894578605	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.33624633	
t Critical two-tail	2.364624252	

value ± 2.36 . Thus we may conclude that there is no significant effect of Demonetization on the RONW ratio of NSE-CNX Banks.

4) E – EARNINGS QUALITY

[Chavda & Trivedi \(2018\) “The effects of Demonetization on the Financial Performance of Indian NSE-CNX Banks Using CAMEL Model”](#)

Investing additional funds forms an important part of the banking function along with lending. In the recent past, banks have been criticized for making most of their money from treasury operation and other investment rather than from core lending operation.

Return on Assets: Net Income / Average Assets

This ratio measures return on assets employed or the efficiency in utilization of the assets. It is arrived at by dividing the Net Income by Average Assets, which is the average of total assets in the current year and previous year. The profitability of the firm is measured by establishing relation of net profit with the total assets of the organization. This indicates the efficiency of utilization of assets in generating revenue. The HDFC Bank in all years is more able to utilize their assets as effectively, compare with remaining Banks, which can be seen from the chart and figures arrived on.

HYPOTHESIS TEST

H0: There is no significant effect of Demonetization on the Return on Assets ratio of NSE-CNX Banks (D=0)

H0: There is significant effect of Demonetization on the Return on Assets ratio of NSE-CNX Banks (D≠0)

Years	SBI	CORP	PNB	BOB	ICICI	AXIS	HDFC	YES
2015-16	0.44	-0.21	-0.59	-0.8	1.34	1.56	1.73	1.53
2016-17	0.38	0.22	0.18	0.19	1.26	0.61	1.68	1.54
Deviation (d)	0.06	-0.43	-0.77	-0.99	0.08	0.95	0.05	-0.01

The above two years Data Bank of Baroda has maximum absolute deviation and YES Bank have minimum Absolute deviation. Thus BOB have maximum effect of Demonetization compared to all sampled Banks. This data have tested using excel Hypothesis Testing tool and the following is the output of excel:

t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means		
	Variable 1	Variable 2
Mean	0.625	0.7575
Variance	1.094828571	0.403507143
Observations	8	8
Pearson Correlation	0.854982344	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	7	
t Stat	-0.623061444	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.276497015	
t Critical one-tail	1.894578605	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.552994031	
t Critical two-tail	2.364624252	

The above data are tested using t-Test for Paired Two Sample Mean. This is two tail test (($D \neq 0$) assuming $\alpha=0.05$, in the above table observed t value is -0.62 which is between the t critical value ± 2.36 . Thus we may conclude that there is no significant effect of Demonetization on the Return on Assets ratio of NSE-CNX Banks

5) L-LIQUIDITY:

The business of banking is all about borrowing and lending money. Timely repayment of deposits is of crucial importance to avoid a run on a bank. With co-operative banks going under frequently and with the recent collapse of GTB (Global Trust Bank) investors have become extremely sensitive. They are alert; they rush to the bank to withdraw money at the slightest hint of trouble. In such a scenario, even false rumors could wreak havoc with a bank. Hence, banks have to ensure that they always maintain enough liquidity.

Liquid assets as a percentage of total assets measures of the liquidity position of the bank to meet the amount of total assets. We have seen in chart that liquidity situation of Bank of Baroda Bank is quite good.

HYPOTHESIS TESTING

H0: There is no significant effect of Demonetization on the Liquid Assets to Total Assets ratio of NSE-CNX Banks ($D=0$)

H0: There is significant effect of Demonetization on the Liquid Assets to Total Assets ratio of NSE-CNX Banks ($D \neq 0$)

Chavda & Trivedi (2018) “The effects of Demonetization on the Financial Performance of Indian NSE-CNX Banks Using CAMEL Model”

Years	SBI	CORP	PNB	BOB	ICICI	AXIS	HDFC	YES
2015-16	7.41	7.41	11.03	19.94	8.31	6.34	5.49	4.97
2016-17	6.36	10.11	12.26	21.65	9.81	8.36	5.67	9.09
Deviation (d)	1.05	-2.7	-1.23	-1.71	-1.5	-2.02	-0.18	-4.12

t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means		
	Variable 1	Variable 2
Mean	8.8625	10.41375
Variance	23.54602143	25.00356964
Observations	8	8
Pearson Correlation	0.950654114	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	7	
t Stat	-2.822480703	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.012840845	
t Critical one-tail	1.894578605	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.025681691	
t Critical two-tail	2.364624252	

In the Liquid Assets to Total Assets ratio concern, YES Bank has maximum absolute deviation and HDFC has minimum Absolute Deviation. Thus YES Bank has maximum effects of Demonetization whereas HDFC Bank has least effect. The above two years Data are tested using excel Hypothesis Testing tool and the following is the output of excel:

The above data are tested using t-Test for Paired Two Sample Mean. This is two tail

test (($D \neq 0$) assuming $\alpha=0.05$, in the above table observed t value is -2.82 which is not lies between the t critical value ± 2.36 . Thus we may conclude that there is significant effect of Demonetization on the Liquid Assets to Total Assets ratio of NSE-CNX Banks

XII. FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

- ❖ In Capital Adequacy Ratio, HDFC Bank have maximum Absolute deviation whereas BOB does not have any deviation. Thus we can inference that the HDFC Bank has significant effect of Demonetization.
- ❖ So far as RONW Ratio is concerned, BOB Bank has maximum Absolute deviation whereas SBI have minimum Absolute deviation. Thus we can say that the BOB Bank has maximum effect of Demonetization and SBI Bank has least effect of Demonetization.
- ❖ In Gross NPAs to Total Assets perspective, YES Bank has maximum Absolute deviation whereas BOB have minimum Absolute deviation. Thus we can inference that the YES Bank has significant effect of Demonetization and BOB Bank has least effect of Demonetization.

- ❖ So far as RONW Ratio is concerned; BOB Bank has maximum Absolute deviation whereas SBI have minimum Absolute deviation. Thus we can say that the BOB Bank has maximum effect of Demonetization and SBI Bank has least effect of Demonetization
- ❖ For ROA Ratio, Bank of Baroda has maximum absolute deviation and YES Bank have minimum Absolute deviation. Thus BOB have maximum effect of Demonetization compared to all sampled Banks.
- ❖ In the Liquid Assets to Total Assets ratio concern, YES Bank has maximum absolute deviation and HDFC has minimum Absolute Deviation. Thus YES Bank has maximum effects of Demonetization whereas HDFC Bank has least effect.

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